

Research

IoT based Agriculture Monitoring System Using Arduino and Node MUC

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Abstract: Agriculture is practiced in every nation and is a science as well as a talent for cultivating plants. In today's world, agriculture must also keep up with the advancement of technology. China is leading the globe in the expansion of its facility agricultural sector. Its ecosystem control technology, however, is still in its infancy and has a low intelligence level. Promoting the use of contemporary information technology in agriculture will address a number of issues that farmers are now experiencing. The loss in output is caused by a lack of precise information and communication. These issues are addressed in our study. This solution offers a facility agricultural ecosystem based on IOT an intelligent monitoring platform foundation and system structure. The switch from conventional farming to modern farming will be sped up by this. Additionally, this offers a chance to build new technologies and services for IOT (internet of things) farming applications. The Arduino and Node MUC charges the smart agriculture by using the IoT system. It has a DC motor, moisture sensor, temperature sensor, and humidity sensor. This structure starts examining the degree of moisture and humidity. The sensors are used to detect the water level, and the system automatically begins watering if the level is below the range. The sensor works in accordance with the change in temperature degree. IoT also displays information about humidity and moisture level along with the date and time. It is also possible to change the temperature measurement dependent on the type of crops grown

Keywords: Agriculture, Internet of Things (IoT), Arduino, monitoring, irrigation system

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Accepted: 21 February, 2023; **Published:** 20 March, 2023

How to cite this article: Benine Ramzi , Qing Lv (2023). IoT based Agriculture Monitoring System Using Arduino and Node MUC. North American Academic Research, 6(2), 211-218. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7754171>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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1. Introduction

The importance of agriculture in a region's economic growth is significant. Agriculture is a vital industry [1]. The objective of advancing agriculture is essential given the global trend toward new technology and its deployment. The field of agriculture is the subject of several studies and when we go deeper we find that reduced groundwater recharge and decreased soil moisture or even the reverse are only a few of the issues that affect agriculture. Consumers also have higher expectations to protect and enhance natural resources for nutritious food that is high in quality. Thus, Small gadgets are being employed in the agricultural field more frequently as a result of the development of smart agriculture is considered a compulsory solution to this issue. Since we live in the era of technology, it is high time to monitor and manage many of the gadgets we use from a variety of locations. The shift from traditional to modern agriculture is now taking place, and it is highly necessary to have contemporary material conditions and apply modern science and

technology to the process. The system may well be extensively used in practice and has high stability, dependable precision, an easy-to-use user interface, and economical costs [2]. This IoT-inspired system will apply and integrate sensors, actuators and data transmission technologies on these devices to optimize the connectivity infrastructure already in place. This has resulted in the establishment of IoT through the confluence of tools for data collecting, analysis, and modification, automated command, integrated devices, connectivity, consistency, consistency and safety [3]. This concept paired with such a sizable scale actual farm concept will result in a sizable network that satisfies the requirements of contemporary automation and supervision of all equipments. For easy lifestyle in farming, IoT is indeed and anticipated to have a significant positive impact on slightly elevated farm and certain other production sectors [4], [5]. The implementation and use of IoT technology in hardware for cultivating sanitary veggies is the study's novel addition. For instance, the indication for automated electrical components to switch between on and off not necessitates control performance directly [6]. Method is presented depending here on IoT network block chain's schematic [7]. Farming becomes more efficient and productive due to modern agriculture, which also helps farmers become even more interconnected and knowledgeable. The global market for automated farming is anticipated to reach about US\$26.76 billion by 2023. Smart agriculture is likely to overtake other agricultural trends into the most significant one in emerging regions. Additionally, it is anticipated that by 2020, the marketplace for smart agriculture would grow from US\$ 730 million to US\$ 2.42 billion. Figure 1 represents the increase understanding as well as growth of IoT initiatives [8]. Therefore, Control technology has been utilized in the agricultural section to address these challenges. Despite being used at the scientific scale, it is not made available to landowners as a commodity so that they can profit from their supplies. So, the topic of this essay is the development of agricultural applications and the extend of its uses based on IoT.

2. Literature Review

By using wireless sensing connections, the authors put out a report to continually note the characteristics of the soil and ambient conditions. At numerous places all around the field, various input sensor nodes are installed. These characteristics may be controlled by every remote system or networking site, and activities are carried out by connecting sensors, Wi-Fi, and cameras to microcontrollers. The well-being of the landowner is served by the creation of this idea as a commodity [9]. While the manual process of verifying the characteristics is still in use today and is among the earliest methods in the agricultural section. The landowners manually compute the measurements and check all the characteristics in this way [10]. In another hand, [11] concentrates on designing gadgets and solutions that harness the benefits of a wireless sensor-based plan to handle, show, and notify people. In confirmation of that, [12] it attempts to use automated and IoT technology to make farming smarter. Modern GPS Device remotely operated robots with the ability to identify humans and execute duties like watering, mowing, and humidity monitoring are the standout characteristics. This article is also reinforced by [13] where the authors offered a study where the linked device ESP8266 of the Microchip communicates such data on the web over the Internet. This improves automatic watering since the water tank may be turned either on or off based on the data provided to the processor, as well as being used to measure the nitrogen and chlorophyll contents of leaves utilizing LDR and laser technology. For [14] where it puts out a concept regarding how an automatic operation of watering was created to maximize the utilization of water towards plants. Besides that, an access point also manages to sense data and all that is to analyze the restrictions which have been employed for lowering the amount of danger in agriculture.

3. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram of the proposed system which gives information of the required modules is shown in Figure 1.

Fig: 1 Block Diagram of Smart Agriculture Model.

3.1 Main Switch

It serves to switch the power source of the whole system on and off, shown in Figure 2. A switch's role in in this process is to either generate or break the connection. An electrical appliance's current can be turned on or off by using a switch.

Fig: 2 Main switch.

3.2 Five Volt Regulator

It is used to supply the Arduino network, which includes the LCD and sensors. With a fixed output voltage of 5V and three terminals, it is a three-terminal linear voltage regulator IC that may be used in a variety of applications. It contains internal current limiting and heat cutoff functions, can supply upwards of 1.5 A of current (with a heat sink), and only needs a small number of external elements to operate properly, shown in Figure 3.

Fig: 3 Five Volt Regulator.

3.3 Node MCU

It serves as the second highest crucial component of the system and can address many of the project's demands on its own. It is an open-source network built on the ESP8266 module that connects items and enables data flow to the system via the Wi-Fi protocol. Additionally, by including some of the most crucial microcontroller functionalities, such as GPIO, PWM, and ADC, and making it detachable for study purpose, shown in Figure 4.

Fig: 4 Node MCU.

3.4 Arduino Nano

The Arduino Nano is a small, feature-rich, and breadboard-friendly board based on the ATmega328 or ATmega168. It has approximately the same features as the Arduino Duemilanove but comes in a different package. All chip activities are suspended when the oscillator is in the Power-down state, waiting for the next interrupt or hardware reset. The contents of the registry are nonetheless kept. The asynchronous timer keeps running when the rest of the device is in power-saving mode, allowing the user to monitor a timer base. The ADC Noise Reduction mode turns off the CPU and all other I/O modules except from the asynchronous timer and ADC to decrease switching noise during ADC conversions. While the rest of the device is sleeping in standby mode, the crystal/resonator oscillator is operating. As a result, highly quick startup and low power consumption are both possible. The primary oscillator and the asynchronous timer both continue to operate in extended standby mode.

It is the highest crucial component of the system and is in charge of keeping everything running smoothly. It serves as the work's brain and offers a variety of communication ports for connecting to a computer, or other chipsets. UART TTL (5V) serial connection is offered by the ATmega328 and is accessible on digital pins 0 (RX) and 1 (TX). It is also detachable for study purpose, shown in Figure 5.

Fig: 5 Arduino Nano.

3.5 Sunlight Sensor

The Arduino activates a few LEDs when there is insufficient light. Arduino can determine how bright or dark it is by observing the output of a photo-resistor, a resistor that changes in response to light, shown in Figure 6.

Fig: 6 Sunlight Sensor.

3.6 Motor Output

A motor's power is calculated as the product of its speed and torque. The output power in watts is about equal to $9.57 \times (\text{torque}) \times (\text{rpm})$. It is the AC interface used to connect the hydraulic system, it may either removed or attached depending on the needs of study purpose, shown in Figure 7.

Fig: 7 Motor Output.

3.7 Motor Control Relay

A relay is a switch that is electrically operated. One sort of solid-state relay uses an electromagnet to mechanically activate a switch, however many relays use a different type of operating principle. When more than one circuit has to be controlled by a single signal or when a separate, low-power signal is needed to operate each circuit independently, relays are used. By duplicating and retransmitting the signal from one circuit on another, the first relays acted as amplifiers in long-distance telegraph circuits. It has a cubical shape that manages how much electricity a motor receives. It is made to operate and stop a motor securely and to prevent overloads. It functions as a relay to operate the hydraulic system, and an LED is put above to show whether it is on or off, shown in Figure 8.

Fig: 8 Motor Control Relay.

3.8 Moisture Sensor

Soil moisture sensors calculate the volumetric water content of the soil. Because the direct gravimetric measurement of free-soil moisture necessitates the removal, drying, and weighting of a sample, soil moisture sensors measure the volumetric water content indirectly by using some other property of the soil as a proxy for the moisture content, such as electrical resistance, dielectric constant, or interaction with neutrons. Since the connection between the measured property and soil moisture might vary depending on the environment, including the kind of soil, temperature, and electric conductivity, calibration of the relationship is required. The reflected microwave radiation, used for remote sensing in agriculture and hydrology, is influenced by the moisture content of the soil. Both farmers and gardeners can use portable probes. It is used to gauge how much water is present in the soil and is also detachable for study purpose, shown in Figure 9.

Fig: 9 Moisture Sensor.

3.9 16x2 LCD

With a 16x2 LCD, 2 lines can each show 16 characters. Each character on this LCD is presented using a 5x7 pixel matrix. Humidity, moisture, motor condition, and brightness are printed on a 16 x 2 LCD with blue lighting. The LCD brightness may be changed by turning the circular knob, which is a variable resistor, shown in Figure 10.

Fig: 10 16x2 LCD.

3.10 DHT-11 Sensor

The temperature and humidity of the atmosphere are measured using a temperature sensor (DHT-11). A fundamental, extremely affordable digital temperature and humidity sensor, the DHT-11 is seen in Figure 3. It measures the ambient air using a thermistor and a capacitive humidity sensor, then splits off a digital output on the data pin. The electrical resistance between two electrodes is measured by the DHT-11 to compute relative humidity. A simple, extremely affordable digital temperature and humidity sensor is the DHT-11 sensor (Digital Temperature and Humidity). It measures the humidity in the air using a transistor and a capacitance humidity sensor, and it outputs a digital signal on the data pin (no analog input pins needed). It is employed to gauge the state of the weather. Additionally, it is also can be taken off for study purpose, shown in Figure 11.

Fig: 11 DHT-11 Sensor.

3.11 DC Water Pump

Direct current pumps can use power from a motor, battery, or solar panel to move fluid in a variety of ways. The DC voltages that motorized pumps often employ are 6, 12, 24, or 32 volts. In solar-powered DC motors, photovoltaic (PV) panels containing solar cells are utilized to produce direct current when they are exposed to light. It is a little DC water submersible motor. It is employed to provide long-distance plants with water. The water pump is attached to using the pipeline. Three soil samples and one pipeline are also needed for the modern agricultural concept, shown in Figure 12.

Fig: 12 DC Water Pump.

4. Working

Under various circumstances, the smart farm monitoring system is tested. The soil is tested using a soil moisture sensor under all climatic circumstances, and the findings are properly interpreted. Readings of the moisture output are obtained and updated under various weather situations. The wireless communication is made possible thanks to Wi-Fi. The resistivity of the soil is the only factor that influences the readings of soil moisture sensors. When the sensor first becomes wet, its value is 0. The detected value is transmitted to the microcontroller through Node MCU, and the motor

pump turns off as a result. On dry soil, the highest threshold value is 1023. When the sensor's measured value hits the threshold, the microcontroller activates the relay, turning on the motor. The motor pump automatically turns ON and OFF when plants receive enough amount of water.

5. Advantages

It is inexpensive to buy and simple to maintain. The necessary components are readily available. Utilizing the internet to check the status of a laptop or smartphone provides benefits. Even without a farmer present, the information remains current. The gathered information is updated, keeping the farmer informed of the crop's condition. Additional sensors can be used to obtain crop information that are more precise and effective.

6. Conclusion

IoT will improve intelligent farming. The technology can monitor and manage the irrigation system by forecasting the humidity and soil moisture levels. IoT helps enhance time management, water management, crop monitoring, soil management, and pesticide and insecticide control in several areas of farming. Additionally, this technology reduces the amount of labor required by humans, streamlines agricultural methods, and promotes smart farming. In addition to the benefits this system offers, smart farming may, with only a single touch and no work, aid in expanding the farmer market.

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